

Rethinking mental illness: Healing and recovery in the DSM

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An open access initiative by Psychreg Ltd
ISSN: 2515-138X

The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM) has been a cornerstone of diagnostic practices in mental health since its inception, offering a structured framework for identifying and categorising mental health conditions. Despite its utility, the DSM has faced criticism for its static and categorical approach, which often fails to capture the dynamic nature of mental health and well-being. Traditionally, individuals with stable or well-managed mental health conditions remain classified as mentally ill due to their inclusion in the DSM, raising questions about the appropriateness of such labels. This article examines the limitations of the DSM's diagnostic system, focusing on its implications for clinical practice and the broader approach to mental health. It highlights the importance of recognising mental health as a continuum, where individuals may experience fluctuations in well-being influenced by genetics, life events, and environmental factors. The inclusion of specifiers such as “in partial remission” and “in full remission” in the DSM represents progress toward acknowledging the fluid nature of mental health. The discussion also underscores the need to shift perspectives within the mental health field to emphasise healing and recovery over static diagnoses. By reframing remission as a significant milestone rather than an endpoint, clinicians can reduce stigma and empower individuals to pursue well-being without fear of permanent labelling. Embracing a recovery-oriented model fosters growth, resilience, and the potential for fulfilling lives, challenging traditional notions of mental illness and advancing more compassionate and effective approaches to care.

Keywords: classification; DSM; mental health; recovery; well-being

The Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM) is an essential resource for mental health professionals, offering a comprehensive framework for categorising and diagnosing mental health conditions (Phillips & Raskin, 2021). Since its inception in 1952 by the American Psychiatric Association (APA), the DSM has undergone several revisions to reflect advancements in scientific knowledge and clinical practice. The current edition, DSM-5, published in 2013, represents a significant milestone (e.g., LeBeau et al., 2022), incorporating extensive research findings and clinical expertise to provide detailed diagnostic criteria for a wide range of mental disorders. However, despite its utility, the DSM is not without limitations. It provides a static snapshot of mental health at a specific point in time, which may not adequately capture the dynamic and evolving nature of mental well-being. The reliance on categorical diagnoses has also been criticised for oversimplifying the complexities of mental health, potentially leading to misdiagnosis or underdiagnosis (e.g., Azavedo, 2021). Moreover, the DSM's focus on symptoms and behaviours may not always reflect the underlying causes or mechanisms of mental disorders.

Mental health is best understood as existing on a continuum rather than as a binary state of being either well or unwell (Lomas & VanderWeele, 2022). This spectrum includes a wide range of experiences, from optimal well-being to severe mental illness, and acknowledges that an individual's mental health can fluctuate over time due to various factors such as genetics, life experiences, and environmental stressors. For example, an individual diagnosed with generalised anxiety disorder (GAD) who has achieved stability through therapy and coping strategies might no longer meet the DSM's criteria for "mental illness". Yet, they may still benefit from ongoing therapeutic support to maintain their well-being. This scenario underscores the complexity of mental health classification and the need for a more nuanced approach that considers individual circumstances and experiences. Understanding the distinction between acute and chronic mental health conditions is crucial when considering DSM classifications. Acute conditions are typically short in duration, often with a sudden onset, characterised by intense symptoms that may require immediate intervention. Chronic mental health conditions, on the other hand, are persistent and long-lasting, often with a gradual onset and enduring symptoms.

The DSM includes specifiers that provide additional context regarding the course and severity of mental health conditions. Two specifiers particularly relevant to this discussion are "in partial remission" and "in full remission." "In partial remission" is used when a person's symptoms have significantly improved but do not meet the full criteria for remission. "In full remission" is when symptoms have improved to the extent that they no longer meet the diagnostic criteria for the disorder.

Implications for clinical practice

Understanding the fluid nature of mental health is crucial in clinical practice, as it allows clinicians to adapt their approach to the evolving needs of individuals. Specifiers like "in remission" highlight that mental health conditions are not static but follow a dynamic trajectory. Individuals may transition from acute flare-ups to chronic phases or from active symptoms to periods of remission, requiring nuanced and responsive care. This understanding influences the clinical decision-making process, guiding the selection of interventions that align with an individual's current mental health status. For instance, during acute phases, immediate interventions such as crisis management and intensive therapy are prioritised, while remission phases focus on preventive strategies to maintain stability and prevent relapse. Recognising these transitions enables clinicians to allocate resources more effectively, ensuring that care is targeted where it is needed most.

An interdisciplinary approach is particularly beneficial in this context. Collaboration between psychiatrists, therapists, and social workers can foster a comprehensive treatment plan that addresses the multifaceted aspects of mental health (Arajärvi et al., 2023). For example, a psychiatrist may focus on medication adjustments, while a therapist works on coping strategies, and a social worker provides support for environmental stressors. Incorporating the fluidity of mental health into clinician training is also essential. Educating practitioners about the importance of

specifiers and the dynamic nature of mental health can enhance their ability to recognise shifts in symptom presentation and respond proactively. Understanding mental health as a dynamic process can improve patient engagement. Framing remission as a milestone rather than an endpoint encourages individuals to actively participate in their care, fostering hope and resilience while reducing stigma. This perspective empowers patients to view mental health management as an ongoing journey, rather than a fixed state (Rajaei & Jensen, 2020), ultimately improving outcomes and satisfaction with care.

Tailoring treatment approaches

Specifiers serve as critical tools for clinicians in customising treatment plans based on an individual's current mental health status (Lenz & Litam, 2023). During acute phases, the focus of care shifts to crisis management and stabilisation, prioritising the immediate alleviation of symptoms and ensuring the individual's safety. Conversely, individuals in remission require interventions tailored to maintaining stability, preventing relapse, and fostering overall well-being. Effective treatment plans must remain dynamic, adapting to changes in symptom presentation to promote sustained recovery over the long term.

Destigmatising remission

Recognising remission as an essential component of the mental health journey, rather than an endpoint, plays a significant role in reducing the stigma associated with mental illness (Pinto-Coelho & Relajo, 2017). Clinicians hold a key responsibility in framing remission as a positive and achievable milestone. By encouraging individuals to seek and adhere to treatment without fear of being labelled as "ill", practitioners can create an environment that normalises the pursuit of mental health care. Moreover, celebrating remission as a meaningful achievement empowers individuals and challenges societal misconceptions about mental health conditions.

Recognising the potential for recovery

The incorporation of remission specifiers into diagnostic criteria highlights the potential for recovery, even in individuals managing chronic mental health conditions. A recovery-oriented perspective shifts the clinical approach from merely managing symptoms to supporting individuals in building meaningful, fulfilling lives. Clinicians can empower individuals by helping them set personalised recovery goals, develop effective coping strategies, and strengthen resilience in the face of challenges (e.g., Gagani et al., 2016). This emphasis on recovery promotes hope, fostering a sense of self-determination and optimism for individuals navigating the complexities of mental health conditions. By embracing the fluid nature of mental health and utilising remission specifiers, clinicians can provide more effective, compassionate, and recovery-focused care while challenging societal stereotypes surrounding mental illness.

Healing and recovery

Healing and recovery are central to mental health, extending beyond symptom management to encompass a holistic view of well-being. Many individuals with well-managed mental health conditions lead fulfilling lives, maintain relationships, and pursue their goals. Importantly, healing and recovery do not necessarily imply the complete absence of symptoms but rather the ability to manage and cope effectively. Research demonstrates that individuals with well-managed mental health conditions can achieve levels of well-being comparable to those without diagnosed disorders (Holst et al., 2024). This finding challenges the traditional notion that a diagnosis permanently labels an individual as "mentally ill." Instead, the recovery-oriented model emphasises growth, resilience, and the capacity for personal transformation, recognising that individuals are not defined by their mental health conditions but have the potential to heal and live fulfilling lives.

Shifting perspectives

There is an increasing need to shift perspectives within both society and the mental health field, moving from a strictly diagnostic approach to one that emphasises healing and recovery. This shift can reduce stigma and empower individuals to seek help without fear of being labelled as permanently “ill”. The movement toward “person-first” language in mental health discussions reflects this shift. Referring to someone as “an individual with schizophrenia” rather than “a schizophrenic” acknowledges the person’s humanity beyond their diagnosis and recognises their potential for growth and recovery. This person-centred approach challenges the stigma associated with mental illness and promotes recovery and empowerment for individuals living with mental health conditions. Recovery is a proactive stance, not a cure for illness. Misinterpreting this can lead to damaging consequences. This distinction is particularly important in the mental health field, where support often comes only in moments of acute crisis or at the onset of a significant incident. Yet, it’s those navigating the grey areas of clinical-case management, often overlooked by the system, who are in dire need of our help. These situations should be seen as the real crisis in mental health care.

In discussing mental health, the terms “mental health”, “mental illness”, and “disorder” are often used interchangeably, but precision in language is crucial as it shapes our understanding and approach to mental health issues. This understanding hit home for me when I finally read *I Am Not Sick, I Don’t Need Help!* by Xavier Amador (2012), a book that my brother gave to my parents during my first psychiatric admission in high school. Avoiding it for years, I feared it would bring back painful memories of that admission. Yet, when I did read it, I found it enlightening, especially in its discussion of how individuals with severe insight loss often cling to an image of themselves before their illness.

Everyone has their limitations, often described as deficits or ‘weaknesses.’ While some may view these terms negatively, they’re an integral part of the human experience. These challenges, though difficult, can illuminate brighter areas of our lives. Amador addresses this ‘brokenness,’ especially in those with severe mental health disorders. He acknowledges the struggles that are visible to others and those that are more covert, hidden away from public view. As a therapist, I often contemplate the balance between aiding clients and avoiding fostering dependency or learned helplessness. It’s a delicate balance, focusing on the broken aspects of their lives that might never fully heal, while also fostering independence and resilience. This involves acknowledging that some goals might be unreachable due to functional impairments, and treatment should focus on enhancing quality of life rather than just symptom management.

There is a spectrum of functional impairments, ranging from those who can achieve goals with minimal assistance to those whose health is so unstable that they pose a danger to themselves or others. Understanding this spectrum is crucial in providing appropriate care and support. Treatment should not just focus on managing symptoms, but on strengthening the actual, broken points in a person’s functioning. Why? Because treating the symptom alone is like putting out a house fire without rebuilding the home. Our goal should be to create pathways for individuals to maintain their desired quality of living. Some people never experience relief from their symptoms, due to chronicity or untreatable impairments. Not every symptom is rooted in a diagnosis; sometimes, flaws in our personalities govern the expression of our limitations. Refocusing treatment to target these weak points in functioning, regardless of the symptom, is crucial. I have seen clinicians and peers dwelling on unresolved and chronic symptoms as if strengthening a person’s weaknesses in functioning wouldn’t help them move forward in their healing.

In 2024, clinicians should be approaching the subject of mental health discourse with a nuanced perspective. Empathy, acceptance of imperfection, and empowerment have a high currency among people seeking new therapists. This article offers an evidence-based, practice-oriented exploration of the requisite skills for therapists to facilitate self-management while astutely identifying scenarios where clients may necessitate additional assistance. An empirically grounded foundation in therapy embraces the universality of human emotions. Recognising that feelings such as joy, sadness, stress,

or anxiety are innate to the human experience enables clinicians to foster a therapeutic environment grounded in empathy. The research underscores the importance of empathetic listening, whereby therapists actively attend to and validate their clients' emotional experiences. A salient facet of contemporary therapeutic practice lies in the empowerment of clients by dispelling the notion of perfectionism. The literature on positive psychology and resilience substantiates that individuals can thrive through self-acceptance and adaptability (Bohlmeijer & Westerhof, 2021). Therapists facilitate this process by guiding clients to embrace their imperfections as part of their unique mental health journey (Brooks et al., 2021).

The language of empowerment

Effective communication is pivotal in encouraging self-management (Salemons et al., 2020). It is prudent to employ language that empowers clients by focusing on their experiences rather than diagnostic labels (Ibrahim et al., 2024). This practice aligns with evidence suggesting that constructive language fosters self-efficacy. Empirical findings in psychotherapy emphasise the efficacy of collaborative goal setting. Therapists engage clients in a collaborative process to establish achievable, client-centred goals. This approach emphasises client agency and investment in their mental health journey.

Strength-based interventions, supported by a substantial body of evidence, accentuate the positive attributes of clients and their innate resilience. Such an approach enables therapists to highlight and cultivate the strengths of their clients, thus promoting self-management. Mindfulness and self-compassion practices (e.g., Guttman & Relajo-Howell, 2022), drawn from empirical research, equip therapists with tools to facilitate clients' self-management. These practices encourage individuals to be kind to themselves and to engage in incremental steps toward improved mental well-being (e.g., Shanafelt et al., 2020).

Recognising when clients need more assistance

Beyond fostering self-management, therapists must possess the insight to identify circumstances where clients may require additional support. Such scenarios include escalating universal emotions, persistent struggles with self-acceptance, language-related impediments, feelings of being overwhelmed, challenges in cultivating resilience, and client requests for alternative approaches. In these instances, therapists should consider referring clients to specialised resources or interventions.

In the contemporary landscape of mental health awareness, therapists are entrusted with promoting self-management while vigilantly discerning when additional assistance is warranted. A comprehensive skill set, informed by empirical evidence and practice-oriented strategies, forms the bedrock of this therapeutic paradigm. By embracing universal emotions, empowering through imperfection, employing empowering language, and recognising the nuanced needs of clients, therapists can effectively navigate the multifaceted domain of mental health with a fresh perspective.

CONCLUSION

While the DSM remains an indispensable tool for clinicians, it is essential to recognise that mental health is not a static state but a dynamic and evolving aspect of each person's life. The potential for healing and recovery underscores the importance of moving beyond labels that define individuals solely by their past diagnoses. Acknowledging this fluidity enables clinicians to approach care with greater nuance, tailoring support to the unique journeys of each individual.

By embracing a more holistic view of mental health, the field can foster a culture of understanding and empowerment. This shift calls for integrating recovery-oriented principles into diagnostic practices, prioritising person-centred care, and challenging the societal stigma that often accompanies mental illness. Such changes will not only improve the quality of mental health care but also inspire hope and resilience in those navigating their mental health journeys.

Adopting this perspective has implications that extend beyond the clinic. It encourages policymakers to craft inclusive and supportive frameworks, educators to promote mental health literacy, and communities to build environments where individuals feel safe seeking help. Together, these efforts will lay the foundation for a more compassionate, equitable, and effective mental health system, ultimately helping countless individuals achieve fulfilling lives marked by growth, stability, and well-being.

Acknowledgements: None declared

Conflict of interests: None declared

Funding: None declared

Ethical approval: Not applicable

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